

Beyond the Echo Chamber: Making the case for relational pedagogy where it's least welcome

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Recently, I have had the privilege of attending several international conferences on relational, inclusive, student-centred pedagogies. Inevitably the conversation turned to the power of meaningful connection between teacher and student to enhance engagement, outcomes and belonging ([Bovill, 2020](#)). I have heard passionate talks about care and connection and as I look around the room I see many nodding heads as like-minded colleagues enthusiastically agree. Filled with a sense of common purpose we all leave with armfuls of affirmation, but increasingly, over the following weeks after these events, I have noticed a quiet sense of futility creep in. The people who turn up already care. The echo chamber is warm and reassuring, yet it risks becoming a trap.

Back in the real-world, outside that bubble, it is not uncommon to watch students drift through courses delivered by academics who still think teaching is a one-way transmission of content. I hear colleagues discussing examples in their institutions where feedback is gathered in a way that reduces students to numbers, where booking student appointments feels transactional, and where classroom cultures are built more on compliance than community. The gap between what we know works, and what's actually happening, is worrying.

Relational pedagogy isn't a 'nice-to-have'.

I argue that we need to start by refusing the framing of relational pedagogy as 'soft' or 'extra'. Building relationships with students is not the icing on the educational cake; it is the cake. We know that student belonging is not a pastoral add-on. It is fundamental to learning, motivation, retention, and wellbeing. When our students feel connected, respected, and safe, they are more likely to engage, take intellectual risks, ask questions, and persist through difficulty. These aren't vague feelings, they are measurable contributors to student success. So why is it still so hard to argue the point of relational pedagogy in some spaces?

Reaching the Unreachable: Three Pragmatic Shifts

1. Talk data, not (only) love.

To shift mindsets, we need to translate relational pedagogy into the language of impact—by linking it to the metrics institutions already prioritise. For example, student perceptions captured in the [National Student Survey \(NSS\)](#), such as “I feel part of a learning community”, are increasingly recognised as meaningful indicators of student engagement. There is growing evidence that stronger responses on such NSS items are associated with improved retention and continuation. These student experience metrics are also considered in the [Teaching Excellence Framework \(TEF\)](#), where they sit alongside institutional data on continuation rates and graduate outcomes. The [Office for Students \(2025\)](#) highlights belonging and learning community as important contributors to both student experience and success in their TEF analyses. This reinforces that relational conditions are not peripheral; they are performance critical. When relational practice moves the needle on Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) such as continuation, graduate outcomes, or TEF narrative evidence, senior leaders listen.

2. Build capacity, not just awareness.

Resistance often masks fear: colleagues who are busy, under-supported or unsure how to change. Offer practical, adaptable resources, such as;

- A free FutureLearn course [The Heart of Teaching: Reflective Practice in Teaching & Learning](#) (Flannery & Scholefield, 2025) which supports educators to build strong, supportive relationships in the classroom, foster inclusivity, and create positive learning environments.
- Bovill’s [“Co-creating Learning and Teaching”](#) approach (2020)
- The [Relationship-Rich Education](#) framework (Kuh & Felten, 2023)
- [Cultivating Relational Accountability in Curriculum Development Approaches](#) a recorded workshop from the University of Calgary (open access)

These resources translate care into concrete practice, without relying on performative warmth, such as forced cheerfulness or extroversion, which not all educators find natural or sustainable.

3. Put more (and different) voices in the room.

Invite students to co-design, co-deliver and critique teaching in real time.

When staff hear how a single moment of care changed (or failed) a learner, the message lands differently, and it generates data we can track.

Beyond the Bubble

The echo chamber still matters. It offers solidarity, scholarship and energy. But its future value depends on changing the conversation inside the room, from feel-good affirmation to strategy for system change. Conference sessions can become action labs where participants leave not with warm applause alone but with a draft KPI map, a ready-to-pilot relational practice, or a cross-institution data-sharing pledge.

Yes, I'll keep showing up for the head-nodding moments. But I'm equally invested in turning that solidarity into leverage, so we can have the tough, metric-savvy conversations beyond the room, the ones less likely to end in applause yet far more likely to move the dial for the students who need us most.

Bovill, C. (2020). *Co-creating learning and teaching: Towards relational pedagogy in higher education*. Critical Publishing Ltd. ISBN: 9781913063818

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